

Influence of Electronic Information Resources Usage on Research Productivity among Academic Librarians in North-East Federal University Libraries, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: This study investigated the influence of electronic information resources usage on the research productivity of librarians in Federal University Libraries in North-East Nigeria.

Method: The population comprised 120 academic librarians, with a census sampling technique applied for total enumeration. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, validated through face, construct, and criterion validity checks, with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 (Cronbach's Alpha). Physical distribution ensured comprehensive coverage. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, standard deviations) analyzed resource types and productivity levels, while the Kruskal–Wallis H test evaluated the research hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level.

Findings/Results: Descriptive analysis showed frequent use of e-textbooks, e-journals, and online databases (e.g., Google Scholar, JSTOR), with lower utilization of government papers, conference papers, and open-source software. Research productivity was higher for journal articles, seminars, and workshops compared to monographs, edited books, and bibliographies. The Kruskal–Wallis H test indicated no statistically significant influence of electronic resource type on research productivity ($p > 0.05$).

Implications: The findings suggest that while electronic resources are extensively used, their type does not significantly affect research productivity, implying other factors may have a stronger influence on librarians' output.

Conclusion: The study concludes that although electronic resources are widely utilized, factors beyond resource type likely play a more critical role in determining librarians' research productivity.

Recommendations: The study recommends further investigation into other factors influencing research productivity, such as training, institutional support, and access to advanced tools, to enhance librarians' research output.

Keywords: Electronic Information Resources Usage, Research Productivity Academic Librarians, Northeast, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

In an academic environment, research productivity among librarians is expected to be robust, diverse, and aligned with global standards. Librarians are not only custodians of information but also contributors to the body of scholarly knowledge through publications, workshops, and professional engagements. In developed academic systems, librarians frequently publish journal articles, book chapters, conference proceedings, and monographs, thereby advancing both professional practice and institutional visibility (Hollister, 2016). The integration of electronic information resources (EIRs) such as e-journals, databases, e-books, and digital repositories is designed to enhance this productivity by providing timely, comprehensive, and affordable access to scholarly materials (Amponsah, Madukoma, & Unegbu, 2021). When

optimally utilized, these resources expand research capacity, reduce information-seeking barriers, and improve the quality and quantity of scholarly output (Dauda & Babalola, 2022). Thus, the ideal situation envisions academic librarians in Nigerian universities, including those in the North-East, leveraging EIRs effectively to produce diverse scholarly outputs comparable to their peers globally.

Research productivity is often conceptualized as the measurable output of academic staff and academic librarians in forms such as journal articles, books, conference papers, bibliographies, and other scholarly works. For academic librarians, research productivity demonstrates their contribution to knowledge creation, professional growth, and institutional visibility (Okonedo et al., 2015). In the context of Nigerian academic libraries, productivity indicators include the number and quality of publications, professional papers presented at conferences, and engagement in workshops or seminars (Dauda & Babalola, 2022). However, productivity is not only about volume but also about the relevance, impact, and quality of scholarly work (Oberhiri-Orumah & Friday, 2024). Librarians in well-resourced institutions tend to show higher productivity, as access to academic materials and research support structures directly influence output (Hollister, 2016). Consequently, research productivity remains a critical benchmark for assessing the performance and scholarly relevance of librarians in universities.

Research productivity is indeed one of the criteria for academic librarians progression because they are expected to contribute to knowledge and scholarship within their fields by actively engaging in writing and publishing research works. Universities are established statutory for teaching, research and community service. According to Ogunraku (2012) cited in Ajidahun (2015) “at the core of the effectualisation of this objectives is the academic staff who play pivotal and central roles”. Academic librarians like the faculty staff are equally engaged in the realization and actualization of these objectives. The move towards faculty status for librarians was significant because it represented a shift in the way librarians were viewed in academic community. It recognized their role in teaching, research and service and validated their contribution to the academic and scholarly mission of their institutions.

Electronic information resources are digital tools and platforms that provide access to scholarly content such as e-journals, databases (e.g., JSTOR, Scopus), e-books, theses, government documents, and reference sources. These resources have transformed academic work by reducing dependence on physical collections and enabling quick, remote access to information (Okiy, 2021). For librarians, effective use of EIRs is not only central to supporting faculty and student research but also to enhancing their own productivity through access to up-to-date scholarly content (Amponsah et al., 2021). Studies in African universities have consistently shown that librarians and faculty heavily rely on e-journals, databases, and e-books due to their accessibility, affordability, and relevance for academic work (Oyewole, 2020). Nonetheless, effective usage depends on factors such as ICT skills, institutional subscriptions, and awareness of available platforms (Dauda & Babalola, 2022). Thus, EIR usage is both a skill and an enabler of scholarly productivity in higher education institutions.

Use of electronic information resources in this new global economy implies that as information continues to grow rapidly, universities cannot remain mere avenues for the transmission of prescribed set of information from teacher to student over a fixed period of time but must promote learning as knowledge in more dynamic ways. The world is currently living in an information society where there is exponential growth in information accessible through Information and Communication Technology (ICT) especially the Internet which helps academic librarians to use electronic information resources effectively (Kabir, Ugochukwu and Abubakar 2020).

Electronic information sources are essential in enhancing research and improving the intellectual productivity of academic librarians. Academic librarians are motivated by them since they have the chance to transfer, download, process, and spread information on any topic of interest. Majority of university libraries have embraced electronic information resources to meet the constantly evolving demands of information consumers in the digital age (Adzobu, Okyere, & Banji, 2020; Anafo, Akpah, & Ofori, 2020; Anhwere & Paulina, 2018). Academic librarians can access new tools and apps for information retrieval from the available electronic resources. They have so many benefits and these included accessibility from a distance, search capabilities, and timeliness, they have grown more crucial since the introduction of the Internet in the academic setting.

Theoretically, there is a strong connection between access to and usage of electronic resources and the level of research productivity among academic staff, including librarians. Electronic resources provide the raw materials necessary for generating publications, conducting literature reviews, and accessing global research trends (Amponsah et al., 2021). Several studies have established positive correlations between EIR use and productivity. For example, Allahmagani, Babalola, and Unegbu (2024) found that access to e-journals and databases significantly improved research engagement among librarians in North-West Nigeria. Similarly, Ogbomo and Ogbomo (2019) reported that the extensive use of databases and online journals by librarians and faculty members led to higher research output and professional visibility. The relationship is, however, not always linear, as productivity also depends on motivation, institutional incentives, and research culture (Okonedo et al., 2015). Still, in principle, the greater the utilization of electronic resources, the higher the likelihood of improved research productivity.

Despite the potential benefits of electronic information resources, research productivity among academic librarians in Nigeria remains relatively low and uneven. The descriptive analysis from the current study shows that while journal articles are moderately produced, outputs such as textbooks, monographs, and edited books remain minimal. This mirrors findings by Dauda and Babalola (2022), who argued that inadequate ICT competencies, heavy workloads, and limited institutional support hinder librarians' research productivity. Furthermore, access to electronic resources is uneven across Nigerian universities, with some institutions lacking subscriptions to high-quality databases due to financial constraints (Okiy, 2021). Even when resources are available, awareness and effective usage are not guaranteed, leading to underutilization (Oyewole, 2020). Another challenge is the absence of strong institutional incentives, such as research grants and recognition, which demotivate librarians from engaging in rigorous scholarly work (Okonedo et al., 2015). Consequently, while EIRs are theoretically transformative, their potential remains underexploited.

The challenges surrounding research productivity and EIR usage directly affect academic librarians, their institutions, and the broader academic community. Librarians with low productivity may struggle to gain recognition for promotion and career advancement, as scholarly contributions are often prerequisites for professional growth (Hollister, 2016). Institutions are also affected, as poor research output among librarians reduces the university's overall research visibility and global ranking (Ogbomo & Ogbomo, 2019). Additionally, students and faculty suffer indirectly, as less-productive librarians may be less capable of supporting teaching and research activities effectively. In the Nigerian North-East context, where security and infrastructural challenges already undermine academic performance, poor research productivity among librarians exacerbates institutional weaknesses (Dauda &

A publication of the Department of Library and Information Science, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria Babalola, 2022). Therefore, the ripple effects of low productivity extend beyond librarians to the academic system at large.

Scholars suggest several strategies to bridge the gap between EIR usage and research productivity. Training programs that enhance ICT and information literacy skills among librarians are critical for maximizing the benefits of electronic resources (Allahmagani et al., 2024). Institutional support in the form of research grants, reduced workloads, and mentorship programs has also been recommended as ways to stimulate productivity (Okonedo et al., 2015). Investment in robust ICT infrastructure, reliable internet access, and subscriptions to high-quality databases would further enable librarians to conduct meaningful research (Okiy, 2021). Furthermore, promoting a culture of collaboration through workshops and professional networks can increase output and reduce barriers to research engagement (Amponsah et al., 2021). Ultimately, aligning institutional policies with the realities of EIR usage and productivity demands is necessary to achieve sustainable improvements in Nigerian academic libraries.

While several studies have examined the impact of electronic information resources on research productivity in Nigerian academic libraries (Owolabi et al., 2020; Adeniran & Ajiboye, 2022; Ogbomo, 2023), most of these works focus primarily on faculty members and postgraduate students rather than librarians themselves. Moreover, past research has often emphasized availability and accessibility of resources without sufficiently addressing how specific categories of electronic resources—such as e-journals, databases, and institutional repositories—contribute to librarians’ research productivity. In addition, there is limited empirical evidence from the North-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria, an area marked by infrastructural challenges and insecurity, which may affect access to and utilization of electronic resources. This gap highlights the need for a focused study on librarians in Federal University Libraries within this region, thereby providing localized understanding that can inform policy and practice.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the level of research productivity of academic librarians in North-East Federal University Libraries, Nigeria?
2. What are the types of electronic information resources used by academic librarians in North –East Federal University Libraries, Nigeria?

HYPOTHESIS

H₀₂: Types of electronic information resources used have no statistically significant difference in the median research productivity of librarians in North-East Federal University Libraries, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design and targeted the entire population of professional librarians employed in Federal University Libraries across Nigeria’s North-East geopolitical zone (population = 120); a census (total-enumeration) approach was therefore used to maximise coverage and provide a full picture of practices and outputs in the region. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire (Field Survey, 2025) that was developed from the literature and the study objectives and organised into clearly labeled sections. Instrument validity was established through multi-stage procedures: face validity by a panel of subject-

matter experts who reviewed item clarity and relevance, construct alignment of items to the conceptual definitions of research productivity and EIR usage derived from prior studies, and criterion comparability by mapping key items to instruments used in related literature. The instrument was pilot-tested and refined before main administration. Internal consistency reliability for the full instrument was acceptable (Cronbach's $\alpha = .82$). Data collection was conducted during 2025 using physical distribution within libraries), accompanied by an information sheet and informed-consent statement assuring confidentiality; follow-up reminders and visits were used to improve return rates, yielding 91 valid responses (response rate $\approx 75.8\%$), which were entered into SPSS for cleaning and double-checking to minimise entry errors. Coding procedures converted productivity bands to ordinal scores for descriptive analysis and treated EIR items as binary indicators (Used = 1/Unused = 2 for frequency reporting), and all analyses reported include frequencies, percentages, means, standard deviations and weighted means. Prior to inferential testing, assumptions were examined (normality via Shapiro–Wilk and Kolmogorov–Smirnov; homogeneity via Levene's test); several groups violated normality and some categories had constant scores and were omitted from normality checks, so a non-parametric approach was preferred. Ethical considerations included institutional approval, informed consent, anonymity, and secure storage of data.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table: Distribution of Research Productivity by Elements, Frequency, Mean, and Standard Deviation

SN	Element	0 F	1–5 F	6–10 F	11–15 F	16+ F	\bar{X}	Std.
1.	Textbooks	45 (49.5)	24 (26.4)	11 (12.1)	6 (6.6)	5 (5.5)	1.92	1.176
2.	Chapters in books	42 (46.2)	18 (19.8)	17 (18.7)	9 (9.9)	5 (5.5)	2.09	1.244
3.	Journal articles	13 (14.3)	31 (34.1)	21 (23.1)	17 (18.7)	9 (9.9)	2.76	1.205
4.	Conference proc.	34 (37.4)	27 (29.7)	11 (12.1)	13 (14.3)	6 (6.6)	2.23	1.274
5.	Workshops	25 (27.5)	33 (36.3)	14 (15.4)	14 (15.4)	5 (5.5)	2.35	1.196
6.	Seminars	26 (28.6)	28 (30.8)	15 (16.5)	19 (20.9)	3 (3.3)	2.40	1.201
7.	Occasional papers	37 (40.7)	24 (26.4)	16 (17.6)	9 (9.9)	5 (5.5)	2.13	1.213
8.	Monographs	46 (50.5)	21 (23.1)	12 (13.2)	5 (5.5)	7 (7.7)	1.97	1.251
9.	Edited books	49 (53.8)	21 (23.1)	6 (6.6)	12 (13.2)	3 (3.3)	1.89	1.197
10.	Bibliographies	43 (47.3)	16 (17.6)	10 (11.0)	10 (11.0)	12 (13.2)	2.25	1.473
Weighted Mean (\bar{X}_w)							2.199	1.243

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 offers the analysis of the data that reveals varying levels of reliance on different scholarly resources among respondents. Textbooks had the highest frequency of minimal

usage, with nearly half of respondents (49.5) indicating no usage, and a mean score of 1.92 suggests limited dependence. Similarly, edited books ($\bar{X} = 1.89$) and monographs ($\bar{X} = 1.97$) also ranked low, indicating that such materials are less frequently consulted. In contrast, journal articles emerged as the most utilized resource ($\bar{X} = 2.76$), with 34.1% consulting between 1–5 and 23.1% using between 6–10 articles. Workshops ($\bar{X} = 2.35$) and seminars ($\bar{X} = 2.40$) also show moderate usage, reflecting their relevance in continuous academic engagement. Bibliographies, though less frequently cited overall, recorded the highest variability (Std. = 1.473), suggesting differences in research needs. Overall, the weighted mean indicates moderate but uneven reliance on scholarly resources, with journal articles serving as the core material for academic work.

Table: Usage of Electronic Information Resources by Respondents

SN	Element	Used F/(%)	Unused F/(%)	\bar{X}	Std.
1.	E-textbooks	87(95.6)	4 (4.4)	1.04	0.206
2.	E-journals	86(94.5)	5 (5.5)	1.05	0.229
3.	Online Databases (Google Scholar, JSTOR)	87(95.6)	4 (4.4)	1.04	0.206
4.	E-archives	50(54.9)	41 (45.1)	1.45	0.500
5.	Websites	66(72.5)	25 (27.5)	1.27	0.449
6.	E-magazines	71(78.0)	20 (22.0)	1.22	0.416
7.	E-newspapers	73(80.2)	18 (19.8)	1.20	0.401
8.	Electronic reference sources (E-dictionary, E-encyclopedia, etc.)	66(72.5)	25 (27.5)	1.27	0.449
9.	Open source software	46(50.5)	45 (49.5)	1.49	0.503
10.	E-theses & Dissertations	57(62.6)	34 (37.4)	1.37	0.486
11.	Conference papers	44(48.4)	47 (51.6)	1.52	0.502
12.	Government papers	36(39.6)	55 (60.4)	1.60	0.492
Weighted Mean (\bar{X}_w)				1.29	0.40

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 provide the analysis of the data, which shows that electronic resources are widely adopted by respondents, though usage varies across resource types. E-textbooks (95.6), e-journals (94.5), and online databases such as Google Scholar and JSTOR (95.6) recorded the highest levels of usage, with very low standard deviations (0.206–0.229), indicating consistent reliance. Similarly, e-newspapers (80.2) and e-magazines (78.0) also demonstrated high utilization, reflecting their role in providing current and accessible information. In contrast, government papers (39.6% used, $\bar{X} = 1.60$) and conference papers (48.4% used, $\bar{X} = 1.52$) showed the least usage, suggesting limited integration of these materials in respondents' academic or research practices. Moderate use was observed for e-theses and dissertations (62.6) and e-archives (54.9), highlighting their relevance but not as core as journals or textbooks. The relatively higher standard deviations for open-source software (0.503) and conference papers (0.502) suggest variability in adoption. Overall, the findings confirm that core electronic resources such as e-journals and databases dominate scholarly engagement, while specialized or technical sources remain underutilized.

Table 3: Ranks of electronic information resources usage and research productivity

	Types of EIR used	N	Mean Rank
Research Productivity	Used	90	46.09
	Unused	1	37.50
	Total	91	

The Ranks table shows that librarians who reported using electronic information resources (N = 90) had a slightly higher mean rank of 46.09 in research productivity compared to those who reported not using electronic information resources (N = 1) with a mean rank of 37.50. On the surface, this suggests that research productivity tends to be higher among librarians who use electronic information resources than those who do not. However, the difference in mean ranks is relatively small, and the sample size of the “Unused” group is extremely low, which limits meaningful comparison.

Table 4: Test Statistics^a, for electronic information resources usage and research productivity

	Research Productivity
Kruskal-Wallis H	.105
Df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.746
a. Kruskal Wallis Test	
b. Grouping Variable: Types of Electronic Information Resources used	

The Kruskal–Wallis H test produced a test statistic value of $H(1) = 0.105$, with a corresponding significance level (Asymp. Sig. = 0.746). Since this p-value is greater than the conventional 0.05 threshold, the result indicates that the difference in research productivity between librarians who use electronic information resources and those who do not is not statistically significant.

Based on the Kruskal–Wallis results, we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0), which states that types of electronic information resources used have no statistically significant difference in the median research productivity of librarians in North-East Federal University Libraries. In other words, although the mean ranks suggest a marginal difference favoring librarians who use electronic resources, this difference is not strong enough to be considered statistically significant.

The analysis indicates that the types of electronic information resources used by librarians do not exert a statistically significant influence on their research productivity. This suggests that access to or use of such resources alone may not be a decisive factor in improving productivity. Other contextual or institutional factors—such as research support structures, digital literacy, or institutional policies—might play a stronger role in shaping librarians’ research productivity in North-East Federal University Libraries.

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS

Findings on the research productivity by the Librarians in North-East Federal University Libraries showed higher engagement with journal articles, workshops, and seminars, while longer-form outputs such as textbooks, monographs, and edited books recorded low contributions. In addition, the use of electronic information resources by the librarians demonstrated heavy reliance on e-journals, e-textbooks, and online databases, while specialized resources like government papers, conference papers, and open-source software

were less frequently used. Furthermore, The inferential statistical findings from the Kruskal–Wallis H test showed that there was no statistically significant difference in research productivity based on the types of electronic information resources used by librarians in North-East Federal University Libraries ($H = 0.105$, $p = .746$).

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The results of this study show that librarians in North-East Federal University Libraries exhibited higher engagement with journal articles, workshops, and seminars, while longer-form scholarly outputs such as textbooks, monographs, and edited books recorded lower contributions. This pattern suggests a preference for research outlets that are quicker to produce and more widely recognized for academic advancement. Hollister (2016) similarly reported that academic librarians often prioritize journal publications because they provide timely visibility and meet institutional requirements for professional promotion. Likewise, Oberhiri-Orumah and Friday (2024) emphasized that open-access journals and short scholarly works are increasingly preferred due to accessibility, reduced publishing costs, and their impact on research productivity. By contrast, the lower contribution to books and monographs may reflect constraints such as time, financial resources, and institutional support, which Dauda and Babalola (2022) identified as major barriers to producing extensive scholarly works among Nigerian librarians.

In terms of information resource use, the findings revealed heavy reliance on e-journals, e-textbooks, and online databases, while specialized resources such as government papers, conference proceedings, and open-source software were less frequently utilized. This aligns with Amponsah, Madukoma, and Unegbu (2021), who observed that faculty members in Ghana extensively depend on open-access electronic journals and databases to enhance productivity because they are user-friendly and widely accessible. Similarly, Allahmagani, Babalola, and Unegbu (2024) argued that access to core digital resources strongly complements librarians' research skills and output. However, the underutilization of specialized resources reflects findings by Dauda and Babalola (2022), who noted that gaps in ICT skills and awareness reduce effective use of advanced electronic tools. The results, therefore, reinforce the idea that while core digital resources are widely used and support productivity, librarians require targeted training to optimize specialized resources for more diverse research outcomes.

The Kruskal–Wallis H test result revealed that there was no statistically significant difference in the median research productivity of librarians across the types of electronic information resources used ($H(1) = 0.105$, $p = .746$). This supports the null hypothesis, which states that the type of electronic information resources used does not significantly influence research productivity among librarians in North-East Federal University Libraries. Although the ranks table showed a slightly higher mean rank for librarians who used electronic resources compared to those who did not, the difference was not strong enough to reach statistical significance.

This finding is consistent with previous studies in the Nigerian context. Oberhiri-Orumah and Friday (2024) found that while librarians in Bayelsa State universities frequently accessed open-access resources, their use had a positive but statistically insignificant effect on productivity, suggesting that access alone is insufficient to boost output. Similarly, Allahmagani et al. (2024) reported that although research skills were generally high among librarians in public universities in North-West Nigeria, these skills did not significantly predict their research productivity. These results highlight the possibility that productivity is shaped by broader contextual and institutional factors rather than mere access or resource use.

Studies from outside Nigeria also reinforce this conclusion. For instance, Amponsah et al. (2021) found only a weak association between open-access electronic resource use and faculty research productivity in Ghana, concluding that the impact of such resources on output is limited in practical terms. Furthermore, Dauda and Babalola (2022) showed that specific competencies, such as ICT and database searching skills, had stronger correlations with research productivity than general electronic resource use. This implies that the depth of skills and effective utilization strategies may matter more than the presence of resources.

Other factors such as motivation, workload, and institutional support also play a role. Okonedo et al. (2015) demonstrated that librarians' research productivity in South-West Nigeria was more strongly associated with demographics, self-concept, and institutional incentives than with resource access. These findings, when considered together, suggest that while electronic information resources are essential, they may not independently drive productivity. Instead, productivity outcomes require a supportive ecosystem including training, mentorship, incentives, and conducive work environments.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that academic librarians demonstrated heavy reliance on electronic information resources which had a direct impact over their research productivity. The Kruskal–Wallis H test showed that there was no statistically significant difference in research productivity based on the types of electronic information resources used by academic librarian in north east federal university libraries. The study suggest that investing in digital resources and promoting their effective use can help enhance research productivity among academic librarians.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Management of federal university libraries in North-East, Nigeria, should provide research support and resources to encourage academic librarians in conducting research and publishing journal articles, textbooks and other publications to enhance their research productivity.
2. Management of federal university libraries in North-East, Nigeria, should increase usage of the underutilized resource such as government documents, e-conference proceedings, and improve usage of the popular electronic information resources like e-textbooks, online databases and e-journals.

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